

Metal Ion Interaction with Penicillins. Part-IX. Equilibrium Study on the Mixed Ligand Complex Formation of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc(II) with Ampicillin in the Presence of Bipyridine and Imidazole

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Equilibrium study on the complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) with ampicillin ($ampH^{\pm}$) in the presence of bipyridine and imidazole (B) indicates the formation of mixed-ligand complexes of the types, $M(amp)(B)$, $M(H_1amp)(B)$ and $M(H_1amp)(B)(OH)$ together with small amounts of binary $M(amp)$ and $M(B)$ complexes. Formation constants of the complexes determined by potentiometric method at $37 \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ in aqueous solution at a constant ionic strength, $I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$) and stability constants of the complexes have been correlated with the modes of coordination of the ligands and the nature of metal-ligand bonds.

The study of the bipyridine and imidazole complexes with transition metal ions is of considerable interest as coordination by these ligands are analogous to the nucleic bases, viz. adenine, guanine, cytosine, thymine and uracil, which form the integral part of the structure of nucleic acids. Ampicillin ($ampH$) being an antibiotic drug of the penicillin family, has growth-inhibiting actions on the microorganisms by causing misreading of the genetic codes at the stage of protein synthesis¹. The genetic codes constitute sequences of three nucleic bases out of the above. As the modes of coordination of the nucleic bases are analogous to those by bipyridine (bipy) and imidazole (im) etc., a potentiometric equilibrium study on the mixed-ligand complex formation of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with ampicillin in the presence of bipy and im as auxiliary ligands will throw some light upon the modes of metal ion coordination by ampicillin in the presence of these typical ligands as well as the nucleic bases. The present communication describes the result of a combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric investigation on the mixed-ligand complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) with ampicillin in the presence of bipy and im (B) as auxiliary ligands in aqueous solution at $37 \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ at a constant ionic strength $I = 0.10 M$ ($NaNO_3$).

(I)

Results and Discussion

Ampicillin (I), in its monoprotoneated form ($ampH^{\pm}$) gives two buffer regions at pH 2–4 and 6–8 respectively due to deprotonation of the COOH and the $+NH_3$ groups in successive steps. In binary systems² the ligand ion, amp^- provides bidentate (N,O) chelation to M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) using the amino nitrogen atom and the amide carbonyl oxygen atom to form $M(amp)^+$ and $M(amp)_2$ complexes in the pH range 3–7. At higher pH (>8), these (N,O) bonded complexes are transformed to (N,N,S) bonded complexes. This transformation takes place through metal ion promoted amide deprotonation, involving the release of proton from the coordinated amp^- ion to form the H_1amp^{2-} ion, which provides terdentate (N,N,S) coordination to M^{2+} ions using the amino nitrogen atom, deprotonated amide nitrogen atom and possibly the thiazolidine sulphur atom.

In calculating the formation constants of $M^{2+}/ampH/B$ complexes (Table 1) by the scogs^{3,4} programme, the following species have been considered to be present in the complexation equilibria: $ampH_2^{\pm}$, $ampH^{\pm}$, amp^- , BH^+ , B, M^{2+} , $M(OH)^+$, $M(OH)_2$, $M(amp)^+$, $M(B)^{2+}$, $M(H_1amp)$, $M(B)(amp)^+$, $M(B)(H_1amp)$ and $M(B)(H_1amp)(OH)^-$. Hydroxo species have been considered, since the buffer regions corresponding to complex formation equilibria and hydrolytic equilibria of M^{2+} (aq.) ions are found to be overlapping. The complexation equilibria have been elucidated on the basis of the speciation curves (Figs. 1 and 2).

Stability of the ternary $M(B)(amp)^+$ complexes are judged from their overall stability constants $\beta_{M(B)(amp)}^M$ and also from their $\Delta \log K_M$ values⁵ calculated using the relation (1),

$$\Delta \log K_M = \log \beta_{M(B)(amp)}^M - \log K_{M(amp)}^M - \log K_{M(B)}^M \quad (1)$$

where, $K_{M(amp)}^M$ and $K_{M(B)}^M$ are the stability constants of bina-

Fig. 1. Speciation curves of $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{ampH}^{\pm}/\text{bipy}$ system (1) ampH_2^+ , (2) amp^+ , (3) amp^- , (4) bipyH_2^+ , (5) bipyH^+ , (6) bipy , (7) Cu^{2+} , (8) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, (9) $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})_2^{2+}$, (10) $\text{Cu}(\text{amp})(\text{bipy})^+$, (11) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})(\text{bipy})$ and (12) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})(\text{bipy})(\text{OH})^-$.

Fig. 2. Speciation curves of $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{ampH}^{\pm}/\text{im}$ system (1) ampH_2^+ , (2) ampH^+ , (3) amp^- , (4) imH^+ , (5) im , (6) Cu^{2+} , (7) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, (8) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, (9) $\text{Cu}(\text{amp})^+$, (10) $\text{Cu}(\text{im})_2^{2+}$, (11) $\text{Cu}(\text{amp})(\text{im})^+$ and (12) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})(\text{im})$.

ry $\text{M}(\text{amp})^+$ and $\text{M}(\text{B})^{2+}$ complexes respectively. Positive values of $\Delta \log K_M$ indicate favoured formation of ternary $\text{M}(\text{amp})(\text{B})$ complexes over the corresponding binary ones.

Due to strongly coordinating nature of the bipy ligand, the binary $\text{M}(\text{bipy})^{2+}$ complexes are formed to the extent of ~95% at the early stages of the reaction in the ternary $\text{M}^{2+}/\text{ampH}^{\pm}/\text{bipy}$ systems (Fig. 1). Distribution profiles of $\text{M}(\text{bipy})^{2+}$, ampH^{\pm} and $\text{M}(\text{bipy})(\text{amp})^+$ indicate the formation of ternary $\text{M}(\text{bipy})(\text{amp})^+$ complexes according to eqm. 2,

in the pH range 4–7. With the rise of pH (>8), the ternary 1 : 1 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{bipy} : \text{ampH}^{\pm}$ mixture undergoes a change of colour from blue (λ_{max} 760 nm) to intense violet (λ_{max} 530 nm). Such a large blue-shift of the absorption maxima of Cu^{2+} indicates an increase of ligand field strength around the Cu^{2+} ion in this complex, obviously due to substitution of the amide carbonyl oxygen atom by the deprotonated amide nitrogen atom⁶ according to equilibrium (3),

This mode of chelation also enables the thiazolidine S atom to coordinate the Cu^{2+} ion. On further rise of pH (~9.5), the solution containing $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})$ complex shows another buffer region and consumes one mole of base per Cu^{2+} ion but there is no detectable spectral change. This

TABLE 1-PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS^a OF THE $\text{M}^{2+}/\text{ampH}^{\pm}/\text{B}$ SYSTEMS WITH $\text{M} = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cu}$ AND Zn AND $\text{B} = \text{bipy}$ AND im IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

Temp. = $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3)

(a) Proton-ligand constants :

	ampH^{\pm}	bipy	im
$\text{p}K_2^{\text{H}}$	2.50	1.32	-
$\text{p}K_1^{\text{H}}$	7.05	4.23	7.06

(b) Metal-ligand constants :

	B	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{amp})}^{\text{M}}$		3.12	3.66	4.79	2.98
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{B})}^{\text{M}}$	bipy	5.92	6.97	7.82	5.15
	im	2.29	2.99	4.21	2.54
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{B})(\text{amp})}^{\text{M}}$	bipy	9.39	11.04	13.10	8.34
	im	5.69	7.13	9.54	5.68
$\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$	bipy	0.35	0.41	0.49	0.21
	im	0.28	0.48	0.54	0.16
$\text{p}K_{\text{M}(\text{B})(\text{amp})}^{\text{H}}$	bipy	9.63	8.37	8.38	-
	im	-	8.45	8.42	-
$\text{p}K_{\text{M}(\text{B})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})}^{\text{H}}$	bipy	10.74	9.97	9.92	-

^aLimits of error = +0.04 in log units.

may be due to loss of a proton from a molecule of coordinated H_2O in the amide deprotonated ternary complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})$ according to equilibrium (4),

Significant lowering of $\text{p}K_w$ of water by about 3 to 4 log units in these complexes provides indirect support to the proposition of sulphur coordination, because $\text{M}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{S}(\text{d}\pi)$ bonding favours the deprotonation of a coordinated H_2O molecule. The ternary $\text{M}(\text{bipy})(\text{amp})^+$ complexes of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes also undergo deprotonation similar to equilibria (3) and (4).

The formation equilibria of ternary $\text{M}(\text{im})(\text{amp})^+$ complexes are different from those of the $\text{M}(\text{bipy})(\text{amp})^+$ complexes. Distribution profiles (Fig. 2) of M^{2+} , imH^+ , ampH^{\pm} , $\text{M}(\text{im})^{2+}$, $\text{M}(\text{amp})^+$, $\text{M}(\text{im})(\text{amp})^+$ indicate the existence of the equilibria (5-9),

Amide deprotonated ternary, $\text{M}(\text{im})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})$ complexes are formed according to equilibria (3) with Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ions only. The existence of the reproportionation equilibrium (9) is evident from the presence of metal hydroxo species $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ in detectable amounts. Ternary $\text{Zn}^{2+}/\text{im}/\text{ampH}$ system is dominated by the hydroxo species, $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$. Binary $\text{Zn}(\text{amp})^+$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{im})^{2+}$ complexes contribute about 20 and 10% and ternary $\text{Zn}(\text{im})(\text{amp})^+$ complexes is formed only about 5% of the total metal ion in this system. In the calculation of formation constants, pH-titration data prior to the commencement of precipitation have only been used.

Like the binary $\text{M}(\text{B})^{2+}$ and $\text{M}(\text{amp})^+$ complexes, the stability constant of ternary $\text{M}(\text{B})(\text{amp})^+$ and $\text{M}(\text{B})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})$ complexes also fall in the Irving-Williams order⁷ : $\text{Co}^{2+} < \text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$. The stability orders : $\text{bipy} > \text{im}$ in regard to the B ligands of these complexes reflect the stronger coordinating power of the bidentate bipy over the monodentate im.

$\text{p}K^{\text{H}}$ values for the deprotonation (eqn. 4) of coordinated water in the $\text{M}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})$ complexes are about 3 to 4 log units lower than the ionic product ($\text{p}K_w$) of water at the experimental temperature. This provides an indirect measure of the extent of π -electron delocalisation from the metals to the π -systems of the B ligands and vacant $d\pi$ orbitals of S(amp) in these complexes.

Experimental

Ampicillin trihydrate, $\text{ampH}^{\pm} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%) (Aldrich) was used as such. Freshly prepared solutions of ampH^{\pm} were used. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled, freshly boiled and cooled, CO_2 -free water. Metal ion solutions were standardised by ion-exchange separation combined with acid-base and complexometric titrations⁸. Carbonate-free NaOH solution⁹ was used as the titrant.

pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 pH meter employing a special glass electrode in conjunction with an SCE. $\text{p}K_w$ of water at the experimental temperature were obtained from literature^{10,11}. Procedure for the pH-metric titrations were the same as described earlier². For the determination of binary M^{2+} -ligand stability constants, the M^{2+} : ligand ratios in the experimental solutions were kept at 1 : 5 and 1 : 10. For studying the mixed-ligand complexation equilibria the M^{2+} : ampH : B (where, B = bipy or im) ratios were kept at 1 : 1 : 1 to ensure the exclusive formation of the simplest 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes only. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated with the aid of scogs programme^{3,4} run on a PC-AT computer system. The constants were refined over several cycles of operation and the values corresponding to the minimum standard deviation in the titre were accepted (Table 1). Complexation equilibria were elucidated with the aid of the speciation curves (Figs. 1 and 2).

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